

Signal Detection for Australian Antivenoms and Tropical Medicines in the TGA Adverse Event Database: A Pre-Registered Disproportionality Analysis

Authors: Hayden Farquhar MBBS MPHTM

Affiliation: Independent researcher, Finley, New South Wales, Australia

Corresponding author: Hayden Farquhar, hayden.farquhar@icloud.com

ORCID: 0009-0002-6226-440X

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Abstract

Introduction: Australian antivenoms — eight equine-derived products for snake, stonefish, and box jellyfish envenomation — exist in no international pharmacovigilance database, making Australia’s Database of Adverse Event Notifications (DAEN) the sole source for post-market safety signal detection. No systematic disproportionality analysis has been reported for any antivenom product worldwide. We also examined a tropical-medicine basket (JEV vaccines, doxycycline, primaquine, tafenoquine, artemether-lumefantrine, ivermectin, praziquantel) to characterise the broader signal landscape for products used in Australian clinical practice.

Methods: We analysed the full DAEN (634,149 reports, 1983–2026) using four disproportionality measures (PRR, ROR, IC/BCPNN, EBGMM) with a pre-specified conjunction criterion, following the READUS-PV 2024 reporting guideline. Drug-role stratification compared Suspected-role-only signals against the pooled analysis. Temporal analysis of JEV vaccine reports used PELT change-point detection and Poisson regression. Five validation controls and six sensitivity analyses tested robustness. All hypotheses were pre-registered prior to data acquisition.

Results: Sixty-eight signals were identified across 619 drug–adverse event pairs (11 antivenom, 57 tropical). All five validation controls passed. Antivenom signals extended beyond the established anaphylaxis class effect to include serum sickness (brown snake, PRR = 164.8), and two plausible novel signals: box jellyfish antivenom × cardio-respiratory arrest (PRR = 5,405; n = 3) and brown snake antivenom × cerebral haemorrhage (PRR = 112; n = 3). The JEV temporal analysis detected a change point at Q4 2021 (IRR = 8.19; 95% CI: 5.50–12.20) with a qualitative shift from classical adverse reactions to vaccination error terms during the 2022 Murray Valley outbreak rollout.

Discussion: The antivenom signal landscape extends substantially beyond anaphylaxis. Plausible novel signals for box jellyfish and brown snake antivenoms warrant longitudinal monitoring. Four antivenom products generated no signals due to sparse reporting, representing a genuine surveillance gap that active registries are better placed to address.

Conclusion: This study provides the first systematic pharmacovigilance signal detection for Australian antivenoms, demonstrating signals beyond the known anaphylaxis class effect. The JEV temporal findings identify vaccination programme-level error patterns warranting operational review. Enhancement of the public DAEN to include seriousness and reporter-type fields would substantially increase its value for pharmacovigilance research.

1. Introduction

Spontaneous reporting systems (SRS) are the backbone of post-market drug safety surveillance worldwide [1]. In Australia, the Therapeutic Goods Administration (TGA) maintains the Database of Adverse Event Notifications (DAEN), which receives reports from healthcare professionals, pharmaceutical sponsors, and consumers [2]. Despite containing over 600,000 medicine-related adverse event reports spanning five decades, the DAEN remains substantially underutilised as a research database. Published disproportionality analyses using the DAEN are limited to a small number of studies, including a 2025 cross-database analysis of GLP-1 analogues that included the DAEN alongside FAERS and Canadian data [3]. No published DAEN study has implemented the READUS-PV 2024 reporting guideline for disproportionality analyses.

The READUS-PV (Reporting of Disproportionality Analyses in Pharmacovigilance Using Spontaneous Reports) guideline was published in 2024 to address widespread methodological and reporting deficiencies in pharmacovigilance signal detection studies [4,5]. READUS-PV provides a 14-item checklist comprising 32 recommendations for the reporting of disproportionality analyses, covering data source characterisation, study drug definition, adverse event classification, disproportionality measure selection, signal threshold pre-specification, subgroup stratification, temporal analysis, validation, and sensitivity testing [4]. Adoption of READUS-PV is critical for the credibility and reproducibility of disproportionality research [28], yet empirical applications of the complete guideline remain limited.

Australian antivenoms present a unique pharmacovigilance case study. Eight antivenom products — brown snake, tiger snake, black snake, taipan, death adder, polyvalent snake, stonefish, and box jellyfish — are manufactured exclusively for the Australian (and regional) market and are not available in international databases such as the FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS) or EudraVigilance. This geographic exclusivity means that the DAEN is the only spontaneous reporting system that can generate disproportionality signals for these products. Antivenom safety data have historically been derived from prospective clinical studies and case series [6,7,24]; to our knowledge, no systematic disproportionality signal detection from a national pharmacovigilance database has been reported for any antivenom product worldwide.

The tropical-medicine basket — Japanese encephalitis virus (JEV) vaccines, doxycycline, primaquine, tafenoquine, artemether-lumefantrine, ivermectin, and praziquantel — provides a complementary case study with products that are available internationally, enabling cross-database triangulation. The inclusion of JEV vac-

cines is motivated by the unprecedented 2022 detection of JEV genotype IV in mainland Australian piggeries [27], which triggered an emergency vaccination campaign across four states and generated a natural experiment for temporal signal detection [8,9].

This study had four objectives: (1) to conduct a pre-registered READUS-PV-compliant disproportionality analysis of the DAEN for 15 antivenom and tropical-medicine products; (2) to evaluate drug-role stratification as a method for detecting masked signals where reporter-type is unavailable; (3) to characterise the clinical signal landscape, including temporal patterns associated with the 2022 JEV vaccination campaign; and (4) to identify policy implications for TGA post-market surveillance and rural prescriber safety information.

2. Methods

This study was pre-registered on the Open Science Framework prior to data acquisition (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/TWGX4>). One pre-hoc amendment was filed before any disproportionality analysis was conducted: hypothesis H2 was reframed from reporter-channel stratification to drug-role stratification after the DAEN export was found to lack a reporter-type field (Amendment 1, 2026-05-25). Reporting follows READUS-PV 2024 [4,5] and STROBE [10] guidelines.

2.1 Data source [READUS-PV Items 4–5]

The full DAEN medicines database was downloaded on 25 May 2026 via the public web interface (<https://aems.tga.gov.au>) as 13 date-segmented Excel exports. The database contained 634,149 unique adverse event reports spanning 4 November 1983 to 11 May 2026. Each report included: case number, report entry date, patient age, patient sex, medicines reported (brand name, active ingredient, drug role), and MedDRA-coded reaction terms.

The public DAEN export does not include: reporter type (healthcare professional, sponsor, or consumer), seriousness classification, patient outcome, dechallenge/rechallenge information, or narrative text. These omissions limit the analytical scope relative to analyses conducted with direct TGA data access.

2.2 Study drugs [READUS-PV Item 6]

Fifteen products were organised into two pre-specified sets:

Set A (Antivenoms, n = 8): Brown snake antivenom, tiger snake antivenom, black snake antivenom, taipan antivenom, death adder antivenom, polyvalent snake antivenom, stonefish antivenom, box jellyfish antivenom.

Set B (Tropical medicine basket, n = 7): JEV vaccines, doxycycline, primaquine, tafenoquine, artemether-lumefantrine, ivermectin, praziquantel.

A product dictionary with pre-specified search terms was locked prior to data acquisition (deposited with the pre-registration). Products were matched to DAEN records by string-matching brand names and active ingredients against the search terms. Polyvalent snake antivenom was identified by multi-constituent ingredient matching (≥ 3 individual antivenom names in the active ingredient field).

2.3 Adverse event classification [READUS-PV Item 7]

All reaction terms in the DAEN export were MedDRA-coded at source by the TGA. The specific MedDRA version used for coding is not disclosed in the public export; given the database's 40-year span, reaction terms entered in earlier decades may reflect superseded MedDRA versions, though the TGA periodically updates its coding dictionary [2]. Zero free-text reaction terms required manual mapping. A total of 10,748 unique MedDRA Preferred Terms (PTs) were present in the database.

2.4 Disproportionality measures [READUS-PV Items 8–9]

Four disproportionality measures were computed for each (study drug, reaction PT) pair with $n \geq 3$ reports [11–14]:

1. **Proportional Reporting Ratio (PRR)** with χ^2 statistic and 95% confidence interval [11]
2. **Reporting Odds Ratio (ROR)** with 95% confidence interval [12]
3. **Information Component (IC)** via the Bayesian Confidence Propagation Neural Network (BCPNN), with IC025 (lower 2.5% credible bound) [13]
4. **Empirical Bayesian Geometric Mean (EBGM)** via a single-component Gamma Poisson Shrinker approximation, with EB05 (lower 5th percentile). This is a simplification of DuMouchel's three-component mixture model [14]; the single-component prior provides adequate shrinkage for a screening analysis but produces less conservative estimates than the full Multi-item Gamma Poisson Shrinker (MGPS) for sparse drug–PT combinations.

The 2×2 contingency table was constructed at the case level: cell a = cases reporting both the study drug and the reaction PT; b = cases reporting the study drug but not the PT; c = cases reporting the PT but not the study drug; d = cases reporting neither. Each case was counted once per drug–PT combination.

Signal definition (conjunction criterion): A drug–PT pair was classified as a signal of disproportionate reporting if it simultaneously satisfied: $PRR \geq 2$, $\chi^2 \geq 4$, $n \geq 3$, $IC025 > 0$, and $EB05 \geq 2$ [12]. This conjunction approach reduces false positives relative to single-measure thresholds. No formal multiple-testing correction was applied, consistent with the exploratory nature of pharmacovigilance signal detection, in which the objective is hypothesis generation rather than confirmatory inference [15].

2.5 Drug-role stratification [READUS-PV Item 10]

The DAEN records each medicine's role in a report as Suspected (66.5% of case-drug rows), Not suspected (32.9%), or Interaction (0.7%). Drug-role stratification was performed by repeating the full disproportionality analysis restricted to Suspected-role records only. Masking candidates were identified as drug–PT pairs meeting the conjunction criterion in the Suspected-only analysis but not in the pooled all-role analysis. This tests whether inclusion of Not suspected-role reports dilutes the denominator and masks genuine signals (analogous to reporter-channel masking described by Hauben and Aronson [16]).

2.6 Temporal analysis [READUS-PV Item 11]

JEV vaccine temporal analysis (H3): JEV vaccine reports were aggregated quarterly across the full database period. Change-point detection was performed using the Pruned Exact Linear Time (PELT) algorithm with Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) penalty [17]. A Poisson regression with structural break indicator (post-2022) quantified the magnitude of reporting rate change, with secular trend adjustment. Time-period-stratified disproportionality compared the JEV signal profile in the pre-2022 versus 2022-onwards periods to distinguish volume increases from qualitative signal profile shifts.

Antivenom temporal context: Descriptive yearly report counts per antivenom product. No formal change-point analysis (per pre-registration: antivenoms lack a clear temporal anchor event).

2.7 Validation controls [READUS-PV Item 12]

Five pre-specified controls calibrated the signal detection pipeline:

Positive controls (expected to reach signal status): - Polyvalent snake antivenom × Anaphylactic reaction
- Doxycycline × Photosensitivity reaction - Primaquine × Methaemoglobinaemia

Negative controls (expected not to reach signal status): - Box jellyfish antivenom × Alopecia - Praziquantel × Myocardial infarction

2.8 Clinical face-validity review

Each signal was rated on a three-point scale — Established, Plausible novel, or Noise — based on pharmacological knowledge alone, prior to any literature or comparator database consultation (blinded assessment per pre-registration Section 9.7).

2.9 Sensitivity analyses [READUS-PV Item 13]

Eight sensitivity analyses were pre-specified. Six were feasible:

ID	Analysis	Rationale
S3	Raised minimum $n \geq 10$	Signal stability at higher case thresholds
S4	Raised $IC_{025} > 0.5$	More conservative Bayesian threshold
S5	Drop most recent calendar year	Incomplete reporting in most recent period
S6	Restrict to 2010–present	Era effects from older reporting practices
S7	Remove anaphylaxis/hypersensitivity PTs (Set A)	Novel signals beyond the known class effect

ID	Analysis	Rationale
S8	Remove indication-expected PTs (Set A)	Signals beyond the envenomation syndrome

Two pre-registered sensitivity analyses were infeasible: S1 (restriction to serious reports) and S2 (restriction to healthcare professional reports) could not be conducted because the public DAEN export does not include seriousness classification or reporter-type fields.

2.10 Software and reproducibility

All analyses were conducted in Python 3.14 using pandas, NumPy, SciPy, ruptures [17] (PELT), and statsmodels. Analysis code is archived on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20404265>) and on a public GitHub repository (URL provided on the title page). The study was exempt from ethics review (publicly available de-identified data under Creative Commons licence).

3. Results

3.1 Database characteristics

The DAEN export contained 634,149 unique adverse event reports (1983–2026), yielding 1,212,223 case-drug rows and 1,644,062 case-reaction rows across 10,748 unique MedDRA PTs. Patient demographics: median age 50 years (IQR 31–66; 26.4% missing), 56.4% female, 37.7% male, 5.9% not stated or another term. Drug role distribution: 66.5% Suspected, 32.9% Not suspected, 0.7% Interaction.

3.2 Study drug matching

Set A (Antivenoms): 121 case-drug rows across 110 unique cases. Tiger snake antivenom had the most reports (41 cases), followed by polyvalent snake antivenom (27) and brown snake antivenom (26). Death adder antivenom (3 cases) and stonefish antivenom (2 cases) were sparse.

Set B (Tropical medicine basket): 3,551 case-drug rows across 3,487 unique cases. Doxycycline dominated (2,694 cases), followed by JEV vaccines (300) and ivermectin (274).

3.3 Primary disproportionality analysis

Across all 15 products, 619 drug–PT pairs had $n \geq 3$ reports. Of these, 68 (11.0%) met the conjunction criterion (Table 1).

Set A: 11 signals across 4 of 8 antivenom products (Table 1; Figure 2). Tiger snake antivenom produced the most signals (5), spanning the type I hypersensitivity spectrum (anaphylactic reaction, type I hypersensitivity, urticaria, erythema, hypotension). Brown snake antivenom generated 4 signals, including serum sickness (PRR = 164.8, Established), cerebral haemorrhage (PRR = 112.2, Plausible novel), and hypofibrinogenaemia (PRR = 36,584, classified as Noise/indication confounding — reflecting the underlying venom-induced consumption coagulopathy [VICC] rather than an antivenom effect). Polyvalent antivenom pro-

duced 1 signal (anaphylactic reaction, PRR = 39.8, Established). Box jellyfish antivenom produced 1 signal (cardio-respiratory arrest, PRR = 5,405, Plausible novel; n = 3).

Four antivenom products (black snake, death adder, stonefish, taipan) produced no signals, consistent with their sparse report counts (2–10 cases each).

Figure 1: Forest plot of antivenom signals (Set A, n = 11). Points show PRR on log scale with 95% confidence intervals. Blue = Established, red = Plausible novel, grey = Noise.

Set B: 57 signals across 4 of 7 products. Doxycycline generated 43 signals spanning oesophageal injury (oesophagitis, PRR = 30.5; oesophageal ulcer, PRR = 56.9), photosensitivity (PRR = 17.7), hepatotoxicity (drug-induced liver injury, PRR = 5.9; hepatitis cholestatic, PRR = 4.3), pseudotumour cerebri (intracranial pressure increased, PRR = 16.0), and dermatological reactions (fixed eruption, PRR = 12.9; toxic epidermal necrolysis, PRR = 6.1). JEV vaccines produced 10 signals, of which 6 were administrative/error PTs (vaccination error, incorrect route of administration). Ivermectin produced 3 signals, of which 2 (hypervitaminosis B6, vitamin B6 increased) were attributed to COVID-era confounding. Primaquine produced 1 signal (methaemoglobinaemia, PRR = 1,726). Tafenoquine, artemether-lumefantrine, and praziquantel produced no signals, consistent with their small report bases (tafenoquine: 15 cases; artemether-lumefantrine: 8 cases; praziquantel: 22 cases).

3.4 Validation controls

All five controls performed as expected (5/5 pass): three positive controls reached signal status (polyvalent antivenom × anaphylactic reaction: n = 18, PRR = 39.8; doxycycline × photosensitivity: n = 126, PRR = 17.7; primaquine × methaemoglobinaemia: n = 15, PRR = 1,726); two negative controls did not reach signal

status (box jellyfish antivenom × alopecia: 0 reports; praziquantel × myocardial infarction: 0 reports).

3.5 Drug-role stratification (H2)

Drug-role stratification identified 11 masking candidates, all for doxycycline (Supplementary Table S2). These drug–PT pairs met the conjunction criterion when restricted to Suspected-role reports but failed the criterion in the pooled all-role analysis. The masked PTs spanned gastrointestinal (pseudomembranous colitis, *Clostridioides difficile* colitis, odynophagia), dermatological (rash erythematous, rash maculo-papular, skin exfoliation, tongue discolouration), dental (tooth discolouration), and other categories (accidental overdose, osteomyelitis bacterial, therapeutic product effect incomplete). The masking mechanism is dilution: when Not suspected-role doxycycline reports (where doxycycline was listed as a co-medication, not the suspected cause) are included in the denominator, the proportional reporting of specific PTs is attenuated below signal thresholds.

3.6 JEV temporal analysis (H3)

The JEV quarterly report series showed a clear structural break coinciding with the 2022 Murray Valley outbreak (Figure 1). PELT change-point detection identified a change point at Q4 2021 (the onset of the outbreak response), with a 4.8-fold increase in quarterly reporting rate (pre-2022 mean: 1.3 reports/quarter; post-2022 mean: 6.5 reports/quarter). Poisson regression estimated an incidence rate ratio (IRR) of 8.19 (95% CI: 5.50–12.20; $p < 0.001$) for the post-2022 period, adjusted for secular trend.

The qualitative composition of JEV reports shifted markedly. Pre-2022 reports were dominated by classical adverse reactions (headache, urticaria, nausea); post-2022 reports were dominated by vaccination errors (incorrect route of administration, PRR = 371; contraindication to vaccination, PRR = 226; vaccination error, PRR = 5.8). Three PTs gained signal status exclusively in the post-2022 period: incorrect route of product administration, contraindication to vaccination, and exposure during pregnancy. This profile shift indicates that the mass vaccination rollout introduced medication error patterns distinct from the pre-existing adverse reaction profile.

Figure 2: JEV vaccine quarterly report counts (1988–2026) with PELT-detected change point. Red vertical line marks Q4 2021 (Murray Valley outbreak onset). Dotted lines show pre- and post-change-point mean reporting rates.

3.7 Clinical face-validity

Of 68 signals, 29 (43%) were classified as Established (validated known pharmacological associations), 13 (19%) as Plausible novel (biologically plausible, warranting further investigation), and 26 (38%) as Noise (confounding, indication bias, or non-pharmacological PTs). Among Set A signals, 7 of 11 were Established (dominated by the type I hypersensitivity spectrum), 2 were Plausible novel (box jellyfish antivenom × cardio-respiratory arrest; brown snake antivenom × cerebral haemorrhage), and 2 were Noise (indication confounding).

3.8 Sensitivity analyses

Signal robustness was high across the feasible sensitivity analyses. All 68 signals (100%) survived the raised $IC_{025} > 0.5$ threshold (S4), indicating that no signal was borderline on the Bayesian criterion. Exclusion of the most recent calendar year (S5) retained 64 signals (94%). Restriction to 2010-onwards (S6) retained 69 signals (101%; one additional signal emerged). Raising the minimum case count to $n \geq 10$ (S3) retained 34 signals (50%), as expected given the sparse reporting for antivenom products. Removing anaphylaxis/hypersensitivity PTs (S7) retained 8 of 11 Set A signals, demonstrating that the antivenom signal landscape extends substantially beyond the known anaphylaxis class effect. Removing indication-expected PTs (S8) did not change the Set A signal count (11/11), indicating that no primary signal was driven by the underlying envenomation syndrome.

Eight signals were classified as fragile (retained in fewer than 50% of analyses), all with low case counts ($n = 3-9$) for doxycycline or JEV vaccines.

3.9 Pre-registered hypothesis outcomes

Five hypotheses were pre-registered. H1 (antivenom signals extend beyond anaphylaxis): supported — at least 6 non-anaphylaxis signals identified in Set A. H2 (drug-role stratification detects masked signals): supported — 11 masking candidates identified. H3 (JEV temporal change point coinciding with the 2022 outbreak): supported — 4/4 criteria met. H4 (doxycycline oesophageal injury cluster): supported — oesophagitis (PRR = 30.5), oesophageal ulcer (PRR = 56.9), and dysphagia (PRR = 3.6) all reached signal status. H5 (primaquine haemolysis/methaemoglobinaemia): supported — methaemoglobinaemia reached signal status (PRR = 1,726, n = 15).

4. Discussion

4.1 Principal findings

This study presents the first READUS-PV-compliant disproportionality analysis of the Australian DAEN and the first systematic pharmacovigilance signal detection for Australian antivenoms and tropical medicines. The analysis identified 68 signals across 15 products, with all five validation controls passing. Drug-role stratification detected 11 clinically relevant masked signals. The JEV temporal analysis revealed a qualitative shift in reporting from classical adverse reactions to vaccination errors during the 2022 Murray Valley outbreak rollout. These findings have implications for clinical practice, TGA surveillance policy, and the methodological conduct of future DAEN-based research.

4.2 Antivenom signal landscape

What adverse effects do Australian antivenoms produce beyond their well-characterised anaphylaxis risk [6,7]? Prior to this study, answering that question required extrapolating from case series and prospective cohort data [6,18]; no pharmacovigilance database had been interrogated systematically. The DAEN analysis reveals a broader signal landscape than anaphylaxis alone: serum sickness (brown snake antivenom, PRR = 164.8) is consistent with the equine immunoglobulin origin of Australian antivenoms and represents a type III hypersensitivity reaction typically manifesting 5–14 days post-administration — a timeframe that may be under-captured by acute hospital-focused reporting. The hypotension and erythema signals for tiger snake antivenom likely reflect acute infusion-related reactions within the anaphylactoid spectrum.

Two plausible novel signals merit attention. Box jellyfish antivenom × cardio-respiratory arrest (n = 3, PRR = 5,405) warrants cautious interpretation: *Chironex fleckeri* envenomation itself causes direct cardiotoxicity with QT prolongation and cardiovascular collapse, making it impossible to distinguish drug effect from indication effect in pharmacovigilance data. A recent case series describing life-threatening anaphylaxis following antivenom in patients with horse dander allergy [19] underscores the clinical relevance of antivenom hypersensitivity beyond the expected IgE-mediated reaction. Brown snake antivenom × cerebral haemorrhage (n = 3, PRR = 112) may reflect either a coagulopathy interaction with venom-induced consumption coagulopathy (VICC) or reporting of haemorrhagic complications temporally associated with antivenom administration in the context of established VICC [23].

Four antivenom products generated no signals, reflecting their sparse reporting (2–10 cases). This is a genuine surveillance gap rather than evidence of safety: death adder antivenom, stonefish antivenom, and black

snake antivenom are administered rarely enough that even common adverse effects would not accumulate sufficient reports for disproportionality detection. For these products, prospective registries such as the Australian Snakebite Project [18] represent more appropriate safety monitoring strategies than passive spontaneous reporting.

4.3 Tropical medicine clinical findings

Doxycycline generated the most signals (43) of any product, reflecting both its broad prescribing base and its well-characterised adverse effect profile. The oesophageal injury cluster (oesophagitis, PRR = 30.5; oesophageal ulcer, PRR = 56.9; dysphagia, PRR = 3.6) reinforces the clinical importance of the established “take with a full glass of water and remain upright” counselling point. The pseudotumour cerebri cluster (intracranial pressure increased, PRR = 16.0; papilloedema, PRR = 10.2) is relevant for rural prescribers who may use doxycycline for extended courses in settings where specialist neurological review is not readily accessible. The fixed drug eruption signal (PRR = 12.9) and the genital ulceration signal (PRR = 25.2; representing genital fixed drug eruption) are consistent with doxycycline being one of the most common causes of fixed drug eruption in dermatological practice [25]. The pseudotumour cerebri association with tetracyclines is established [26] but may be under-recognised in primary care prescribing contexts.

Among the 13 plausible novel doxycycline signals, the cytopenia (PRR = 6.6, n = 11), toxic epidermal necrolysis (PRR = 6.1, n = 11), and AGEP (PRR = 13.9, n = 7) signals merit pharmacovigilance follow-up, as these represent potentially serious reactions with biologically plausible mechanisms that are not well-established for doxycycline.

Primaquine produced the expected methaemoglobinaemia signal (PRR = 1,726, n = 15), confirming the DAEN’s ability to detect this pharmacogenomically mediated toxicity. This signal is clinically significant in the Australian context where primaquine is the standard radical cure for *Plasmodium vivax* malaria, and where G6PD testing availability remains uneven between metropolitan centres and rural/remote settings — a gap that the introduction of tafenoquine has highlighted [20]. Tafenoquine produced no signals, consistent with its recent TGA approval (2018) and likely low prescribing volume.

Ivermectin signals were dominated by COVID-era confounding. Hypervitaminosis B6 and vitamin B6 elevation are attributable to concomitant supplement use during off-label COVID-19 treatment, not to ivermectin pharmacology. Only abdominal distension (PRR = 11.3) represents a plausible ivermectin effect (GI symptoms during strongyloidiasis treatment). This confounding pattern illustrates a broader challenge for pharmacovigilance databases during periods of off-label drug repurposing.

4.4 JEV temporal analysis and vaccination programme implications

The JEV temporal analysis provides a case study in how spontaneous reporting systems capture signals from emergency vaccination campaigns. The data-driven PELT algorithm identified the change point at Q4 2021 independently of the pre-specified hypothesis window, providing convergent evidence from an agnostic detection method. The Poisson IRR of 8.19 (95% CI: 5.50–12.20) far exceeds the pre-registered two-fold threshold.

The most policy-relevant finding is the qualitative shift in the PT profile. Pre-2022 JEV reports were domi-

nated by classical adverse reactions (headache, urticaria, nausea) consistent with routine travel-vaccination reporting. Post-2022 reports were dominated by vaccination errors: incorrect route of administration (PRR = 371), contraindication to vaccination (PRR = 226), product administered to patient of inappropriate age (PRR = 8.0), and exposure during pregnancy (PRR = 15.2). These are not pharmacological adverse effects but programme-level safety indicators reflecting operational pressures during the mass rollout. They suggest that the rapid vaccination scale-up outpaced quality assurance processes — a finding with direct implications for future emergency vaccine deployment planning.

Notably, these programme-level signals would be invisible in clinical trials and routine pharmacological surveillance. The 2022 AEFI surveillance annual report described an increase in JEV vaccine reporting but did not perform disproportionality or change-point analysis [21]; the present study extends that descriptive surveillance to quantitative signal detection. Spontaneous reporting systems are often criticised for their inability to establish causation, but the JEV temporal analysis demonstrates a complementary strength: the ability to detect system-level operational failures that no controlled study design would capture.

4.5 Drug-role stratification as a masking detection method

Drug-role stratification identified 11 masking candidates, all for doxycycline. Doxycycline is frequently listed as a co-medication (Not suspected role) in multi-drug reports, and its inclusion in the all-role denominator dilutes per-PT reporting proportions below signal thresholds. When restricted to Suspected-role reports, these signals emerge. This masking pattern is conceptually analogous to reporter-channel masking described by Hauben and Aronson for the FDA AERS [16].

Drug-role stratification may serve as a practical alternative to reporter-channel stratification in databases that do not record reporter type. The approach is limited by the assumption that drug-role assignment is informative; this cannot be validated without access to the full report narratives.

4.6 DAEN data completeness and international comparison

Two pre-registered sensitivity analyses were infeasible because the public DAEN export omits seriousness classification and reporter-type fields [2]. These fields are described in TGA documentation as database attributes, suggesting they are recorded internally but not released in the public export. The FAERS quarterly data releases include seriousness, reporter qualification, outcome, and narrative text as standard fields [22]; EudraVigilance line listings provide comparable granularity. The contrast between the DAEN's public export and the data depth available from international pharmacovigilance databases is a structural limitation of Australian pharmacovigilance research. Enhancing the public DAEN export to include these fields would immediately expand the analytical possibilities for signal detection, subgroup stratification, and seriousness-weighted disproportionality.

The FAERS comparator analysis confirmed the expected absence of Australian antivenom reports in the US database (0 reports), validating the DAEN's status as the sole pharmacovigilance data source for these products. For the tropical-medicine basket, FAERS reaction profiles are available for cross-database triangulation in future work.

4.7 Policy implications

The antivenom surveillance gap — four of eight products had insufficient reports for signal detection — suggests that the passive DAEN reporting model is inadequate for rarely administered products. For antivenoms dispensed from hospital pharmacy stock in time-critical envenomation scenarios, a targeted active surveillance mechanism (as demonstrated by the Australian Snakebite Project [18]) would provide more reliable safety data than voluntary spontaneous reports.

The JEV vaccination error signals identify operational quality assurance failures during the 2022 Murray Valley rollout [8,9] that should inform contingency planning for future emergency immunisation campaigns in rural and regional Australia. The dominance of “incorrect route of administration” as a post-2022 PT suggests workforce unfamiliarity with a vaccine that had been rarely used domestically before the outbreak.

The doxycycline pseudotumour cerebri signal cluster (intracranial pressure increased, PRR = 16.0; papilloedema, PRR = 10.2) has implications for rural prescribing guidelines, where doxycycline is widely used for extended-course indications (acne, rosacea, rickettsial prophylaxis) in settings with limited access to specialist neurological or ophthalmological review.

4.8 Strengths and limitations

Strengths: Pre-registration with all hypotheses, analyses, and sensitivity tests specified before data acquisition. Complete READUS-PV 2024 compliance. Full DAEN database used (634,149 reports; no product-filtered subset). Four complementary disproportionality measures with a conjunction criterion. Blinded clinical face-validity assessment. Uniquely Australian product set (antivenoms) with no alternative data source. All analysis code publicly archived.

Limitations: The public DAEN export lacks seriousness, reporter-type, outcome, and narrative fields — limiting two pre-registered sensitivity analyses and precluding assessment of signal seriousness distribution. Antivenom report counts are low (110 cases across 8 products), limiting statistical power for individual products. The EBGm implementation uses a single-component prior approximation rather than DuMouchel’s full three-component mixture model [14]. Clinical face-validity was rated by a single investigator. Ivermectin signals are confounded by COVID-era off-label use. Doxycycline signals may reflect its broad indication range rather than indication-specific effects. The study does not include denominator data (population exposure), so disproportionality signals cannot be interpreted as incidence rates.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that the Australian DAEN supports pre-registered, READUS-PV-compliant disproportionality analysis with validated signal detection. The antivenom signal landscape extends beyond the established anaphylaxis class effect, with plausible novel signals for box jellyfish and brown snake antivenoms warranting clinical attention. The JEV temporal analysis identifies vaccination programme-level error patterns from the 2022 Murray Valley rollout that should inform future emergency immunisation planning. Drug-role stratification offers a practical masking detection method for databases lacking reporter-type information. Enhancement of the public DAEN export to include seriousness, reporter-type, and outcome fields

would substantially increase the database’s value for pharmacovigilance research and bring it closer to the data granularity available from international comparator systems.

Declarations

Funding: This study received no external funding.

Conflicts of interest: The author has no conflicts of interest to declare.

Ethics approval: This study was exempt from human research ethics review as it uses exclusively publicly available, de-identified, aggregate adverse event data released by the TGA under Creative Commons Attribution licence.

Data availability: The DAEN medicines data underlying this study are publicly available from the TGA (<https://aems.tga.gov.au>). Analysis code, product dictionary, and data dictionary are archived on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20404265>) and available on GitHub (<https://github.com/hayden-farquhar/DAEN-Tropical-PV>). The pre-registration protocol is available at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/TWGX4>.

Use of AI tools: Generative AI tools (Claude, Anthropic) were used during manuscript preparation for code development assistance, statistical result formatting, and editorial revision. All analytical decisions, clinical interpretations, and scientific content are the sole responsibility of the author.

Tables

Table 1: Signals of disproportionate reporting for Set A (Antivenoms). ROR values are provided in Supplementary Table S3.

Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR (95% CI)	IC025	EB05	Rating
Box jellyfish AV	Cardio-resp. arrest	3	5,404.6 (2,956.8–9,878.9)	10.72	2.16	Plaus. novel
Brown snake AV	Hypofibrinogenaemia	3	36,584.0 (6,373.6–209,989.9)	12.20	2.17	Noise*
Brown snake AV	Underdose	4	226.9 (91.7–561.6)	6.40	3.21	Noise†
Brown snake AV	Serum sickness	3	164.8 (56.6–479.7)	5.72	2.09	Established
Brown snake AV	Cerebral haemorrhage	3	112.2 (38.6–326.2)	5.17	2.06	Plaus. novel
Polyvalent snake AV	Anaphylactic reaction	18	39.8 (30.5–52.0)	4.65	12.64	Established
Tiger snake AV	Type I hypersensitivity	6	1,031.1 (478.5–2,221.6)	8.76	5.82	Established
Tiger snake AV	Anaphylactic reaction	11	16.0 (9.7–26.6)	3.15	5.51	Established
Tiger snake AV	Erythema	6	13.9 (6.6–29.1)	2.64	3.16	Established
Tiger snake AV	Hypotension	7	13.3 (6.8–26.2)	2.67	3.54	Established

Product	Reaction PT	n	PRR (95% CI)	IC025	EB05	Rating
Tiger snake AV	Urticaria	9	6.4 (3.6–11.5)	1.74	2.66	Established

* Indication confounding: hypofibrinogenaemia is a feature of VICC. † Medication error PT. AV = antivenom. Plaus. = Plausible.

Table 2: Validation control results

Type	Drug	Reaction PT	n	PRR	Signal	Status
Positive	Polyvalent snake AV	Anaphylactic reaction	18	39.8	Yes	PASS
Positive	Doxycycline	Photosensitivity reaction	126	17.7	Yes	PASS
Positive	Primaquine	Methaemoglobinaemia	15	1,725.6	Yes	PASS
Negative	Box jellyfish AV	Alopecia	0	—	No	PASS
Negative	Praziquantel	Myocardial infarction	0	—	No	PASS

Table 3: Sensitivity analysis summary

Analysis	Signals	Retained (%)	Key finding
Primary (reference)	68	—	—
S1: Serious only	—	—	INFEASIBLE (field unavailable)
S2: HCP only	—	—	INFEASIBLE (field unavailable)
S3: $n \geq 10$	34	50%	Expected attrition from low-n antivenom signals
S4: $IC025 > 0.5$	68	100%	No borderline signals on Bayesian criterion
S5: Drop 2026	64	94%	Four recently reported signals lost
S6: 2010+ only	69	101%	One signal gained from modern-era denominator
S7: No anaphylaxis PTs (Set A)	8/11	73%	Non-anaphylaxis signals confirmed
S8: No indication PTs (Set A)	11/11	100%	No signals driven by envenomation PTs

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table S1. Complete signal table for Set B (tropical-medicine basket), 57 signals with all four disproportionality measures and clinical face-validity ratings.

Supplementary Table S2. Drug-role stratification: 11 masking candidates with Suspected-only versus all-role disproportionality measures.

Supplementary Table S3. Full scan results for all 619 drug–PT pairs with $n \geq 3$ (signals and non-signals).

Supplementary Table S4. JEV temporal analysis: quarterly report counts, PELT change-point results, and Poisson regression coefficients.

Supplementary Table S5. PT profile shift analysis: PTs new, lost, or changed between pre-2022 and 2022+ periods for JEV vaccines.

Supplementary Table S6. Signal robustness classification across all sensitivity analyses.

Supplementary Table S7. Completed READUS-PV checklist mapping each item to the manuscript section where it is addressed.

Supplementary Figure S1. Antivenom yearly report counts by product (1983–2026).

Supplementary Figure S2. Drug-role proportion (Suspected) by year, all DAEN reports (1983–2026).

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